

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CREATIVE THINKING AS AN IMPORTANT COMPONENT OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHER'S PROFESSIONOGRAM

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Abstract

The article considers the role of creative thinking as an integral component of the professionogram of a foreign language teacher. The significance of the creative approach in teaching activities is analyzed, emphasizing its impact on the effectiveness of teaching and the development of students. Modern methods and strategies that contribute to the development of creative thinking among teachers, as well as examples of their practical application, are presented. Special attention is paid to the integration of creative methods into the process of teaching foreign languages, which helps to increase students' motivation and improve learning outcomes. The article emphasizes the importance of striving to improve one's professional competence through the development of creative potential.

Keywords: creativity, creative thinking, creative approach, creative methods, creative product of pedagogical activity, general cultural competence.

Professional training of foreign language teachers in general and the formation of their general cultural competence in particular during training is a complex continuous process that is carried out throughout the entire period of study of students and covers all academic disciplines. The analysis of curricula and educational and professional programs for training foreign language teachers allowed us to identify the stages of formation of their general cultural competence:

- stage 1 involves formation of a theoretical base;
- stage 2 suggests assimilation of general cultural knowledge at the level of reproductions;
- stage 3 includes transferred and independent use of the acquired knowledge, acquired skills and abilities in solving educational research, creative and culture-oriented tasks, tasks of foreign language speech activity and intercultural communication.

At each of these stages, certain components of general cultural competence are formed [4, P. 89].

Taking into account the above-mentioned classification of professional abilities of a teacher, creative thinking belongs to the basic block; this is the list of abilities that is not formed during the professional training of a foreign language teacher, but develops. That is, applicants with a well-formed creative thinking should enter a pedagogical institution of higher education, which should be developed during training sessions; teach students to implement it in various practical situations of an educational nature and test it during practical training in educational institutions [2].

The phenomenon of creativity in all spheres of human life contributes to the success of implementing the professionalism of each specialist, which is emphasized not only by the scientific community. The study of creativity is determined solely by the practice and economic policies of most countries of the world. This is confirmed by the introduction of a pilot study to the international study of the quality of education PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) to identify

the level of creative thinking from more than 80 countries / economies of the world.

Creative thinking in teaching involves the ability to generate innovative ideas, solve problems in novel ways, and adapt to changing circumstances in the classroom. For foreign language teachers, creativity can transform traditional teaching methods into more interactive and enjoyable experiences for students. It allows teachers to develop unique approaches to language instruction that can help students better understand and retain new information.

Creative thinking of a future foreign language teacher is the key to his professional development both at the personal level and at the competence level. In the context of socio-economic changes taking place in our country, pedagogical universities face the question of the quality of training future teachers for productive pedagogical activities. Students learn to independently acquire knowledge, master the skills to perceive new information, comprehend it, and on the basis of this generate new ideas, etc. [2].

Creativity in the methodology of teaching a foreign language today is a modern concept, where creativity is a rather relative concept, the use of which is not limited only to research issues. Most foreign language teachers point out that language education should be linked to "creativity", which means that the learning process should be more creative, where teachers should use more "creative texts" for teaching, which should inspire students to use a foreign language more "creatively" [3].

Strategies for fostering creative thinking can be as follows: professional development workshops can provide teachers with training sessions focused on creative teaching methods and the latest educational technologies, collaborative learning can encourage teachers to collaborate and share their creative ideas and experiences with colleagues; reflective practice can promote self-reflection among teachers to evaluate their teaching practices and identify areas for incorporating more

creativity; resource accessibility can ensure that teachers have access to a wide range of teaching materials and resources that inspire creativity.

The use of modern creative methods of teaching foreign languages in higher education institutions can lead to the acquisition of basic interdependent skills, such as fluency in a foreign language and the formation of communication abilities. As a result of competence-oriented teaching of foreign languages, the student acquires the ability to work with professionally significant foreign language material, independently acquire new knowledge and develop personal creative potential. The results of the study can be used to improve the educational system by combining the creative language activity of the teacher with modern methods of teaching foreign languages to increase the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language and the formation of students' communicative competence, which will improve the current quality of higher education in the training of future specialists [3].

In practice we can apply it during interactive activities like incorporating games, role-plays, and storytelling to make language learning more engaging; in multimedia resources like using videos, music, and digital tools to enhance the learning experience; in project-based learning like assigning projects that require students to use their language skills creatively, such as creating a video or writing a short play; in cultural immersion like designing lessons that include cultural exploration, encouraging students to learn about the cultures associated with the languages they are studying.

Creativity in the structure of competence of a foreign language teacher reflects the creative achievements of the individual at different stages of professional (pedagogical) activity and is understood as the ability to create new professional products and high results of activity due to the realization of creative abilities of the individual. The characteristics of the creative product of the teacher's pedagogical activity are the unusual, novelty, usefulness of the decisions made, as well as the overall productivity of pedagogical activity, which is expressed in the optimal organization of interaction [1].

Integrating creative thinking into the professional development of foreign language teachers has significant implications. It not only improves teaching effectiveness but also contributes to teachers' job satisfaction and professional growth. By fostering a culture of creativity, educational institutions can enhance the overall

quality of language instruction and better prepare teachers to meet the challenges of modern education.

So, creative thinking of a foreign language teacher ensures that they take into account the psychological and age characteristics of students; the use of modern forms, methods, techniques and teaching tools; creating an atmosphere that will contribute to the generation of new ideas and thoughts by students, creating the necessary creative environment; increasing the volume of project, team and group activities in the pedagogical process; combining classical options for organizing educational space with the latest ones; planning and design of educational premises; using new IT technologies, new multimedia teaching tools. We consider the study of the specifics of the formation of the ability to creative thinking in higher education applicants to be a promising direction for further scientific research [2].

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